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Research Article

Formulation And Evaluation of Herbal Face Wash Gel for Acne, Skin Whitening and Scars Treatment

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ABSTRACT

This work is focused on Preparation and Evaluate a cosmetic Herbal Face Wash by using natural ingredient. The cleansing has progressed immensely over several thousand years from simply scraping the skin to an exercise in relaxation and improvement in the skin's health and appearance in the present day. a few years ago, cleansing was done by using a piece of bone or stone to scrape the skin. Behind time civilizations used materials of plant origin along with water for cleansing. Acne is a chronic inflammatory condition of the pilosebaceous unit characterised by increased sebum production by sebaceous glands and aberrant desquamation of hair follicles as a result of rising androgen levels as puberty approaches. Follicular obstruction produces follicular distention, which is commonly accompanied by the bacteria Propionibacterium acnes proliferating and an inflammatory reaction being triggered. The goal of this study was to use Carbomer Ultrez 20 to create and test a herbal face wash gel including extracts of Azadirachta indica (Neem), Curcuma longa (Haldi), Carica Papaya (papaya), Aloe berbadandis (Aloe Vera), Citrus limon (Lemon). The plants have been shown to have antimicrobial, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory properties in the literature. The prepared formulation was tested for a variety of criteria.

INTRODUCTION

India's herbal drug industry is likely the world's oldest medical care system. Herbs have such a long history in ancient India that they are even mentioned in the Vedas, an ancient Hindu religious text. Ayurveda and Unani, two ancient herbal healing systems, deal with the use of herbs

and natural products to treat health problems. Although herbal remedies may appear to be novel to western healers and doctors, the truth is that plant extracts are still used in the Acne has the potential to have long-term emotional and physical consequences. Regardless of the severity of the disease, it is linked to depression and anxiety,

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albeit the psychological symptoms normally improve with treatment. Acne can also leave permanent scarring that is difficult to remove. Today, there is a lot of interest in the Ayurvedic system of medicine all over the world, so the demand for various commonly used medicinal plants in the production of Ayurvedic medicine is growing all the time. Commercial formulations based on medicinal plants, on the other hand, must be safe, effective, and of standard quality ref.no.3,4.

Types of acne

Pimples or spots appear when the skin generates a lot of oil, which allows bacteria to thrive and block the pores, causing swelling and redness. Pimples aren't contagious at all. Out of various kinds of pimples the most common types are as follows:

- **Whiteheads**- Whiteheads are tiny bumps that remain under the skin's surface
- **Blackheads** – Blackheads have a vivid black appearance and rise to the surface of the skin, but they are not caused by dirt. Black heads aren't black because of dirt; they're black because they're black. Keratin, a protein, is oxidized by air in most cases.
- **Papules** – Papules are little pink pimples on the skin that are painful and visible.
- **Pustules** – Pustules (pimples or zits) are red at the bottom and have pus at the top. It can be seen on the skin's surface.
- **Nodules** – Nodules are little bumps on the skin's surface that are easily apparent. They are painful, huge, solid pimples that are visible on the skin surface and exist deep within the epidermis.
- **Cysts** – Cysts are visible on the skin's surface. They're firmly embedded, unpleasant, pus-filled, and prone to scarring ref.no.3,14.

Causes of acne:

1. Hormone levels fluctuate around the time of a woman's cycle.
2. Genetics
3. Using personal care items that are oily or greasy.
4. Acne flare-ups can be exacerbated by stress, which raises the hormone cortisol ref.no.3,14.

Face Wash:

Definition

A cleanser is a facial product it is used to remove makeup, dead skin cells, oil, dirt, and other types of pollutants from the skin of the face. This helps to prevent pores and skin conditions such as acne. A cleanser can be used as part of a skin care regimen together with a toner and moisturizer ref.no.1,13.

Benefits of Face Wash

1. It aids in the removal of dead skin cells, allowing new skin cell.
2. skin a healthy glow.
3. It keeps the skin looking young and healthy.
4. By removing dead skin cells, you might expect your skin to age more slowly ref.no.1,13.

Properties of face - wash:

1. Cleansers with herbs and botanicals that clear the pores and minimize oil buildup are necessary for oily skin. Anti-inflammatory and antioxidant ingredients in these exfoliating cleansers which helps to repair and nourish damaged skin.
2. Sebaceous glands secrete too much sebum, which clogs the pores and makes the skin oilier.
3. It must be both stable and appealing to the eye.
4. Exfoliation stimulates skin regeneration and renewal by speeding up blood circulation

5. It should be able to spread without dragging.
 6. Rather than absorption, its physical action should be that of skin flushing and pore opening.
 7. Herbal face wash is used to cure acne and pimples because of its therapeutic property. Herbal face cleanser, which contains rich plant-based components like neem and turmeric eliminates excess oil without stripping the skin of its nutrients.
 8. It should be stable and should have a good appearance ref.no.1,13,10.
3. Bath and renewal keeping the skin clean and shiny.
 4. For cleansing the skin.
 5. Help plug the pores clear ref.no.1,13,10..

MATERIALS AND METHOD:

Selection and authentication of plant leaves of neem and papaya were collected. Fruits of Nutmeg, alovera, turmeric root, rosewater were collected. Walnut oil is oil extracted from walnuts fruits. The oil contains polyunsaturated fatty acids, monounsaturated fatty acids, and saturated fats, fresh alovera leaves, vit.E, extracted fresh juice from lemon, xanthum gum, rose water shown in table no.1 ref.no.5,6 Table No.1 List of all ingredients with quantity ref.no. 5,11

Applications Face-wash.

1. Anti-aging,
2. Every day, remove any traces of makeup

Table No.1 List of Ingredients with their quantity

Sr. No.	Name of Ingredient		Uses	Quantity (15ml)
	Name	Biological Name		
1.	Neem	Azadirachta indica	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Skin toner, • Reduced dark spots, • fineness, • wrinkle and keep the skin healthy 	2.5 ml
2.	Turmeric	Curcuma longa	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Helps to reduced acne • any resulting scars. 	1.25 ml
3.	Papaya	Carica papaya	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Natural bleaching properties, • lighten darks spot • acne mark 	2.5 ml
4.	Nutmeg	Myristica fragrans	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced pigmentation, • treat oily skin, • acts as natural toner. 	1.25 ml
5.	Walnut	Juglans regia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced dark circles, • moisturizer, • brightness skin 	2.5 ml
6.	Aloevera	barbadensis miller	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Anti-inflammatory, • Reduce pain, • Swelling, 	2.5 ml
			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Soreness of wounds • Injuries 	

7.	Lemon	Citrus limon	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Antioxidant. • Antifungal, • Astringent, • Skin lightning. 	0.5ml
8.	Honey	Apis dorsata, apis indica	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lighten skin, • Moisturizer, • Acts as cleanser, • Useful in sunburn, • Fights acne, • Pimples, • Natural glow 	2.5 ml
9.	Xanthan Gum	Bacterium Xanthomonas campestris	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stabilizer and thickening agent 	1ml
10.	Rose Water	distilling rose petals with steam.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Solvent 	Q.S
11.	Methyl paraben	occurs naturally in several fruits, particularly in blueberries.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preservative 	0.05mg
12.	Propyl Paraben	Propyl paraben	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preservative 	0.03mg
13.	SLS	Sodium Lauryl Sulphate	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Foaming agent 	1.05mg
14.	Vit.E		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • antioxidant, • helping protect cells from damage 	1ml

Preparation of extracts:

Leaves of neem, Leaves of papaya, rhizomes of turmeric, were kept in hot air oven for draying purpose at 45 c and grinded into small pieces by using grinder. Seeds of nutmeg were crushed to make powder. Add some quantities of herbal drugs were weighed and each herb macerated with rose water in conical flask. Dried herbs are mix with rose water by moderate shaking of conical flask. Separately contents were filtered out by using simple filtration method and filtrates were collected in vessels separately shown in fig.no.1.

Figure no.1 preparation of extract

Preparation of Face Wash:

The desired concentration of gelling agent i.e. xanthium gum was weighed accurately and dispersed in hot rose water (not more than 60°C; 50 % weight of the batch size) with moderate stirring, avoiding air entrapment and allowed to soak overnight. Add some quantity of fresh lemon juice was dissolved in few amount of honey by

gentle stirring. Then added desired amount of neem extract, turmeric extract, papaya extract, nutmeg extract, walnut oil and vitamin E capsule. Desired quantity of concentrated herbal extracts were added to the remaining amount of rose water and mixed with above honey & alovera mixture by gentle stirring shown in figure no.2.

Formulation of gel

All ingredients weighed accurately and it is given in Table no. 1. Gels were formulated using Carbopol 940 was dispersed in distilled water with continuous stirring. In another beaker, propyl paraben (0.03mg) and methyl paraben (0.05mg) and sodium lauryl sulphate was dissolved in 5ml of distilled water. The extracts were added into prepared solution and triturated well. The above mixture was then added to the Carbopol mixture and stirred well. Finally propylene glycol and triethanolamine was added to adjust pH 6.9. ref.no.7,1.

Figure No.2 Formulation of herbal face wash

Evaluation

Evaluation parameters of herbal face wash as follows: ref.no.1,2,9,12.

1. Physical evaluation

Physical parameters such as colour, appearance & consistency of formulation were visually checked.

2. Washability

Formulations of herbal face wash were applied on the skin then easily remove and washed with water checked manually.

3. Colour

The colour of the face wash was checked with visual observation.

4. pH

pH of formulation was determined by using a calibrated digital pH meter at constant temperature.

5. Viscosity

The viscosity of face wash was measured by using Brookfield Viscometer.

6. Irritancy test

The face wash was applied on hand on dorsal surface of the skin on 1 sq. cm area and observed in time interval 1 to 2 hrs.

7. Spreadability

Take a two slide draw a 2cm circle on one slide the applied 1gm of face wash formulation on slide give the pressure another slide then taken measurement of Spreadability.

8. Foam test

Taken five test tube mark upto 10ml each test tube takes 1ml, 2ml, 3ml, 4ml, 5ml then add distilled water in all test tube upto 10ml mark. Then shake test tube it produced foamed measured the foam in centimeters.

Figure No.3 Foam Test for Face wash

RESULT:

Herbal Face Wash Gel for acne treatment was prepared and evaluated.

Table No. 2 Evaluation parameters of Face Wash Gel

Sr.no	Parameter	Marketed Formulation	Formulated Product
1	Colour	Green	Green
2	Consistency	Semi solid	Semi Solid
3	Wash ability	Good	Good
4	Ph	6.9	5.9
5	Viscosity	1690cp	1520cp
6	Irritation	Non Irritant	Non Irritant
7	Spreadability	1.8	1.9
8	Foam test	Passed	Passed

CONCLUSION

Now a days herbal formulations have growing demand in the world market. The herbal face wash was prepared from various herbs like Neem, Papaya, Turmeric, Nutmeg, Aloe vera, Honey, and the soothing agent as Xanthan gum used for formulation. It gives beneficial effects to the face. The herbal face wash is one of the most well recognized for acne treatments, herbal face wash not only moisturized, they also used as a cleanser. It is mostly used for oily and dry skin physiology. Which provides numerous essential nutrients to the required for maintaining the normal skin functioning. It remove dead skin cells and potentially reduce the occurrence of clogged pores, ingrown hairs, and acne and also promotes the natural glow to the skin. The various parameters like colour, pH, consistency,

washability, irritability and spreadability evaluation parameter was checked hence, from the present investigation it was found that the formulated herbal face wash was found to be more effective as compared to the marketed face wash

AUTHORS CONTRIBUTION:

Manuscript are written by Ms.Shraddha Shivde and Mr.Rahul D. Ahire. Mr.Karan G. Pawara. Ms.Anita G. Valvi. designed and performed research by Ms.Shraddha Shivde and Mr.Rahul D. Ahire. Mr.Karan G. Pawara. Ms.Anita G. Valvi.

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